

On Dicyanobisbiguanidinium Complexes of Rhodium(III) and Iridium(III)

S. P. GHOSH* and R. K. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, Science College, Patna University,
Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 22 September 1986, revised 23 October 1987,
accepted 13 November 1987

RAY and Sengupta¹ reported the formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{CN}^-)_2]^+ 1/2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{BigH}^+ = \text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}_6$. The analogous rhodium(III) and iridium(III) complexes are not known. In the present communication we describe the preparation and characterisation of dicyanobisbiguanidinium complexes, $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{M} = \text{Rh}$ and Ir .

Experimental

Dicyanomono-bisbiguanidinium monobiguanidine metal(III) monohydrate, $[\text{M}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Rh}^{\text{III}}$ or Ir^{III}): The dichlorobisbiguanidinium metal(III) chloride^{7,8} (~0.5 g) was dissolved in hot water (50 ml) and refluxed with KCN (0.5 g) on a steam-bath slowly for 2–3 h, when a dull-white product separated gradually. The product was filtered, washed with water and dried over CaCl_2 , (70–80%).

comparative inertness of Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} than Co^{III} towards ligand replacement reaction can be attributed to their larger ligand field splitting energy and higher stability in their complexes than those of Co^{III} ^{5,6}. However, dichlorobisbiguanidinium complexes $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{BigH}^+)\text{Cl}_2] \cdot \text{Cl}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Rh}^{\text{III}}$ and Ir^{III})^{7,8} conveniently undergo substitution reaction with KCN in basic medium giving insoluble dicyano complexes, $[\text{M}(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{Big})(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $[\text{M}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{OH}^-$. Attempts to isolate chloride or sulphate salt of the above complex by the action of dilute acid was unsuccessful.

It has been found that $[\text{Rh}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ on prolong digestion with 2N HCl on a steam-bath gave a light yellow solution which on concentration gave the amidinourea (Amu) complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{AmuH}^+)_2\text{CN}^-]_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where, $\text{AmuH}^+ = \text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}$). The formation of amidinourea by hydrolysis of coordinated biguanide with dilute HCl is quite reasonable⁹.

The solid reflectance spectra of the complexes do not display distinct electronic band in visible region 350–600 nm. In ultraviolet region, the complexes display strong absorption below 340 nm due to back-bonding from metal to antibonding orbital of CN group¹⁰. The complexes are diamagnetic and quite stable in air.

The IR spectra of complexes display a broad and strong band at 3300–3450 cm^{-1} attributed to

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
	M	N	O	H	Cl
$[\text{Rh}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	27.41 (27.54)	45.01 (44.90)	19.98 (19.25)	04.23 (04.01)	—
$[\text{Ir}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	36.48 (36.28)	15.32 (15.55)	03.68 (03.25)	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{AmuH}^+)_2\text{CN}^-]_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	22.95 (23.80)	23.16 (23.60)	13.01 (13.36)	04.01 (03.90)	15.42 (15.32)

Tetra-amidinourea di-μ-cyanodirrhodium(III) chloride pentahydrate, $[\text{Rh}(\text{AmuH}^+)_2\text{CN}^-]_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: $[\text{Rh}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (~0.03 g) was suspended in 2N HCl (20 ml) and refluxed on a steam-bath when the compound went into solution giving light yellow solution. The solution was concentrated to 5–6 ml on a steam-bath when a cream white precipitate separated. The product was filtered, washed with water and dried as above.

Results of elemental analysis are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that the trisbiguanidinium complexes³ $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \cdot 1.5\text{SO}_4$ (where $\text{M} = \text{Rh}$ and Ir)^{3,4} unlike their Co^{III} analogue do not undergo substitution reaction conveniently with KCN. The

$\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, ν_{NH} , and $\nu_{\text{NH}}^{\text{II}}$ ^{11,12}. The strong and sharp band at 2100 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Rh}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and at 2095 cm^{-1} in case of $[\text{Ir}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ suggest the bonding of CN group through C atom in both the complexes^{12,13}. The complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{AmuH}^+)_2\text{CN}^-]_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ though ionic but is sparingly soluble in water, suggesting the dimer character of the molecule. The IR spectra of the complex display a strong band at 2175 cm^{-1} which occurs in the range of carbon bonded bridging cyanide group¹⁴. The spectra also display a strong band at 1680 cm^{-1} (br) attributed to ν_{CO} stretch of amido group of amidinourea. A new strong and broad band at 1070 cm^{-1} is attributed to ν_{NCO} vibrations of amidinourea molecule. In far-infrared region, $[\text{Rh}(\text{Big})(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{CN}^-)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays a sharp peak at 485 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 530 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{Rh}-\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Rh}-\text{N}}$ ¹⁵. In case of iridium complex, these bands are weak and observed at 320(sh) and 520(cm^{-1}). In case

* 6B Rajendra Nagar, Patna-800 016.

of $[\text{Rh}(\text{AmuH}^+)_2(\text{CN}^-)]_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, a medium band at 570 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 450 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{Rh-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Rh-C}}$, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The award of Junior Research Fellowship by U.G.C. to one of the authors (R.K.P.) is thankfully acknowledged.

References

1. P. RAY and N. R. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 201.
2. P. RAY and N. K. DUTTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 621.
3. S. P. GHOSH and A. I. P. SINHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 179.
4. S. P. GHOSH and A. I. P. SINHA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1703.
5. R. G. PEARSON and F. BASOLO, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1967, p. 124.
6. P. HURWITZ and J. K. KUSTIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 823.
7. S. P. GHOSH and P. BHATTACHARJEE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 573.
8. S. P. GHOSH and P. BHATTACHARJEE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 501.
9. P. RAY and N. KUNDU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 811.
10. L. H. JONES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 277; 1965, **4**, 1472.
11. L. J. BELLAAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley, New York, 1957.
12. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1970.
13. A. P. GINSBERG and E. KOUBEK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1186.
14. A. HAIM and W. K. WILMARTH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 509.
15. L. H. JONES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **26**, 1578.

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Alkanals by Hexacyanoferrate(III) catalysed by Osmium(VIII)

G. K. KHETAWAT and G. D. MENGHANI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 16 June 1980, revised 31 March 1986, accepted 12 August 1986

KINETICS of oxidation of ethanal, propanal and n-butanal by hexacyanoferrate(III) in sodium carbonate-bicarbonate buffer have been studied. The reaction is zero order in oxidant, first order with respect to both alkanal and Os^{VIII} , and the order with respect to alkali has been found to be ≈ 0.5 . The data suggest that the anion of the hydrate of alkanal is involved in the oxidation. The thermodynamic parameters ΔE , PZ and ΔS^* were evaluated.

A review of literature shows that some work has been done on the kinetic studies of oxidation of alkanals under acidic conditions^{1,2} and ethanal

under alkaline conditions³. It was therefore thought fruitful to undertake kinetic studies of oxidation of a series of alkanals by hexacyanoferrate(III). This communication presents data on the OsO_4 -catalysed oxidation of ethanal, propanal and n-butanal.

Experimental

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (E. Merk, A.R.), ethanal (AnalaR), propanal (Riedel), n-butanal (Fluka A.G.), osmium tetroxide (Johnson and Mathey) were used. All other chemicals used were either A.R. or G.R. grade. The catalyst was prepared by dissolving a known weight of OsO_4 in 0.05 M KOH solution.

The reaction was studied in presence of carbonate-bicarbonate buffer solution (prepared by mixing equal volumes of 0.025 M solutions of each sodium carbonate and sodium bicarbonate). The reaction was carried out in an adequately thermostated cell of a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter using filter no. 42. The unconsumed hexacyanoferrate(III) was estimated after known intervals of time without disturbing the reaction mixture.

Results and Discussion

The rate of oxidation is found to be of zero order in [hexacyanoferrate(III)] and independent of the initial concentration of oxidant (Table 1).

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)

[Alkanal] = 3.93×10^{-3} M, $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 8.33 \times 10^{-4}$ M, $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]^{**} = 4.16 \times 10^{-3}$ M, pH = 10.5, Temp. = 35°

$[\text{Fe}(\text{ON})_6^{3-}] \times 10^4$ M	$K_0 \times 10^7$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹		
	Ethanal*	Propanal**	n-Butanal**
3.93	7.40	11.26	5.29
3.00	6.66	11.22	4.87
2.66	6.85	11.60	5.95
2.33	6.66	10.59	4.77
2.00	6.66	10.61	4.40

The first order dependence on [substrate] is established by fairly constant values of $K_0/[\text{substrate}]$ (Table 2). OsO_4 catalyses the reaction. Constant values of $K_0/[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ (Table 3) and linear plot of $\log K_0$ vs $\log [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ with a slope of unity shows first order dependence of the rate on $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$. The rate of oxidation marginally increases with the increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$. A plot of $\log K_0$ vs $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ is linear with a slope of 0.5, suggesting half order in alkali. The values of activation parameters (Table 6) are close to the values given by Bakore and Narain⁹, suggesting C-H bond cleavage in the rate determining step.

From the fact that hexacyanoferrate is consumed but shows zero order dependence on $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$, it is reasonable to assume that hexacyanoferrate(III) does not react directly with substrate and its action